

Deliverable 2.2

Workpackage 2

Responsible Partner: 36-INSA

Contributing partners: 2-AGES, 7-SZU, 14-UT,
23-UoS, 25-NUIG, 33-NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.2

Preliminary data collection on ARG prevalence and ARG background load in the compartments analysed so far (T2.4)

Description of the task

For this task is planned that all samples collected in WP2-T3 are analyzed. Initially, the starting date of task JRP17-R2-**WP2-T4** [*Quantify clinically relevant antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) in the tested compartments (qPCR; qPCR arrays)*] was M27, but it had to be postponed to M34 and it will end by M42. In the original project proposal, a selection of genes associated with antimicrobial resistance (AMR) to specific classes of antibiotics were intended to be chosen for their quantification by qPCR: *tet(M)*, *tet(W)*, *tet(Z)*, *bla*_{TEM-type}, *bla*_{SHV-type}, *bla*_{CTX-M-type}, carbapenemase-encoding genes, *sul1*, *sul2*, *su3*, *erm*-like genes, plasmid-mediated quinole resistance-encoding genes, *mcr*-variants and *int1*. However, as explained in the 12M Report, for the detection of ARGs the qPCR assays were substituted upon agreement with the Supervisory Board (SSB) by a gene enrichment approach, which presents higher sensitivity than the one proposed initially in **WP2-T3.2**. This gene enrichment approach is known as advanced AMR marker profiling.

Description of deliverable

Beyond the COVID pandemic, the delay in this task was due to the time invested in the decision process of performing a gene enrichment (= target enrichment) approach.

In contrast to the target enrichment approach described in the original project proposal, the current strategy includes the analysis of as many exDNA samples as possible, as well as some selection of total DNA samples for comparison purposes, both being provided by each of the sample collector within WP2. Unlike the former qPCR-based strategy, in this new methodology the load of ARGs might be inferred from the number of sequencing reads that cover each detected ARG sequence.

In this deliverable we firstly performed a pilot experiment to confirm that the target enrichment approach worked better than conventional shotgun metagenomics for the detection of ARGs. We collected two wastewater samples, one from the inlet and one from the outlet at a biological wastewater treatment plant (I1 and E1, respectively) in the vicinity of the Austrian HOAL. Afterwards we extracted the extracellular DNA and the total DNA following the protocols described in the Annex 15 to the D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP2.1. Last, both DNA types were used for the conventional shotgun metagenomics and the advanced AMR marker profiling (=target enrichment). Results showed that the conventional shotgun sequencing followed by ametagenomics analysis enabled pathogen identification and AMR marker detection. However, the vast majority of the reads were unassigned (>95.5 %) and their compensation would be a major cost factor. Therefore, targeted sequencing with a panel that includes all AMR markers within ARESdb seemed the best alternative to shotgun metagenomics.

Overall, the advanced AMR marker profiling will allow us to detect due to its higher sensitivity over qPCR and conventional shotgun metagenomics, which environmental compartments (sources) have which ARGs and at what level. Later, this will allow us to identify possible points of intervention to decrease the AMR spread via free exDNA. Once we obtain the results from all WP2 collectors, it will be also possible to compare the data obtained at different European regions, and later on we expect to pinpoint potentially different ARG hotspots. In addition, these data might be of further use for WP5 and WP6.

One of the advantages of this methodology has been the possibility of increasing the number of samples to be tested by target enrichment, which will allowed us to include the detection of a greater diversity of ARGs and, therefore, we will obtaining a more realistic picture of the resistances that exist in each compartment. ARGs in complex environmental matrices like soil are usually underrepresented in metagenomic analyses and this gene enrichment strategy in particular is essential to do so. The current target enrichment methodology has been established with the collaboration of a start-up company in Vienna (ARES Genetics), which to our knowledge, possesses one of the biggest AMR database in the world together with a cutting edge technology based on capture probes. Furthermore, this new target enrichment approach will be complemented by a new 16S metagenomics strategy that will take part of **WP2-T6**. In contrast to the project proposal, the 16S metagenomics analysis will be performed on the entire region (V1-V9) of the 16S and in the same sample selection as for the target enrichment.